

SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL INFORMATION MODELING SKILLS OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION FIELDS

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Annotation: *This article presents the scientific theoretical basis of the formation of professional information modeling skills on the basis of didactic conditions that form professional information modeling skills in the process of improving the professional training of students of higher educational institutions in technical education areas based on innovative technologies, the student's ability to think and Great importance is attached to improving their qualities, their ability to work in a team.*

Keywords: *Technology, digital technology, didactic conditions, model, professional information modeling, component, procedural, procedural component, construction*

At the same time as the demands of the future engineers in our country are being adapted to the expansion of their modern technological knowledge and the technologies that are becoming popular on the basis of innovative technologies, the idea of the economy of tomorrow - the economy of knowledge and high technologies - is being strengthened in the minds of people.

The modern stage of the formation of professional information modeling of future engineers is characterized by a systematic approach to the study of complex scientific and technical problems based on the use of a complex of digital information and technologies and the search for a solution.

We created the process model of information modeling skills in three parts: the goal block, the strategic block, and the result block. Let's talk about the content and components of these structural blocks, and their interrelationships.

The goal block is the main starting point of the process model, and subsequent blocks are organized based on this goal. When defining the purpose of the model, the needs of the main subjects of the process of

forming information modeling skills among students (acquiring information modeling skills, the need to use them, requirements for acquiring this skill in practical activities, etc.) are taken into account. It is determined based on the requirements of the society (the development of information and communication technologies, the needs for the skills of using ICT in professional activities, the requirements determined on the basis of the ability to widely use the possibilities of increasing work efficiency). Based on these two factors, we determined the goal of the model as "Increasing the efficiency of preparing future engineers for professional activity based on the formation of information-modeling skills." Also, types of information models such as tabular, graphic, dynamic, static, hierarchical, network are mentioned. These models are widely used in the work of future engineers, and in preparation for this process, students are introduced in detail to each type of model and the experiences of working with them.

The principles to be followed in preparing future engineers for information modeling activities are as follows:

- the principle of coordinating the integration of activities;

- the principle of self-development of students;
- the principle of social responsibility;
- principle of social competence;
- the principle of continuous development;
- balancing principle;
- the principle of mobility in the use of information.

The following didactic conditions are required for preparing students for information modeling activities:

- integration of methodical, informative and modeling activities of students and teachers into a single didactic system;
- to include the stages of solving professional issues based on information technologies in the information-modeling activities of students;
- implementation of an interactive opportunity between the subject and ICT for information collection, processing, processing, transmission, modeling;
- presentation of educational materials used in the educational process by means of animation, video, etc.;
- modeling of module programs, technical and audio-visual means of teaching, which condition the integrity of methodical, informational and subject areas of information-model preparation.

In the strategic block of the model, the stages of implementation of information-modeling are presented.

Stage 1: the constructive formative stage includes the creation of conditions for the implementation of the model, the implementation of measures to solve the specified tasks. This stage provides various information technology skills, including the use of application software packages, in modeling the activities of the future engineer. At this stage of the work, the student develops the skills of receiving, processing, transforming and creating experimental data of his research. To implement activity modeling, the future engineer must master new information technologies, including the use of computer technologies, which is one of the didactic conditions, and modern computer modeling systems that combine special information and methodological support [7].

The block of technical problems solved in the process of modeling corresponds as much as possible to the tasks of the professional activity of an engineer, increases the motivation of students to acquire a profession and acquire knowledge, and forms the skills of making constructive decisions and implementing them in practice.

The ability to refer to normative data for modeling, to search for it, and to give it a professional assessment should also be acquired [4].

By considering the same tasks with the help of modern software, as a result of obtaining information and obtaining calculation results, automation [6] saves time compared to mechanical calculation. In such a situation, practical information skills with a subject-subject description are successfully formed.

In the process of modeling problem solving using algorithms, the student uses additional information. It was the result of reflexive activity in terms of self-awareness and self-study, and was qualitatively different from other professionals in its adaptation to the profession. At the same time, the educational process is based on the system of principles and pedagogical conditions of content implementation in terms of content, choice and convenience. The implementation of modeling at this stage ensures the implementation of didactic functions: the student strengthens the ability to use computer programs and information systems during independent study of theoretical material [7], receives the necessary feedback from the pedagogue, as a result of which education takes on a person-oriented appearance, an environment of trust and mutual understanding is created . Stage 2: During the implementation of the corrective-diagnostic stage, the implementation of the model and the results are monitored. The software-technological and organizational-activity components of the model are compared with the analysis stage, the results of additional input

and strengthening of existing conditions show their impact on the information-educational space of the higher education institution. In the process of implementing the model, it is desirable to create a creative environment, to independently develop a research technical task in the process of planning and searching for alternatives that require additional research work in the diagnosis of creative competencies, to suggest how to solve the problem.

Stage 3: In the presentation-summarization stage, students systemize the research results using computer programs and draw conclusions. Summarizes the received information in the form of visual materials (presentations, illustrations, diagrams, plans, etc.). At this stage, the future engineer's information competence should include components such as the ability to make fundamentally new decisions in unexpected situations, to find unconventional solutions to problems and questions (with the help of information and communication technologies) [5, 6]. The content of forming students' information-modeling skills, which constitutes the main content of the model, is also included in the strategic block. That is, the author's program, system of methods (cases, innovative technologies, independent activities of students) are covered.

The ability to communicate and interact in an online e-learning environment requires intellectual-communicative skills. As a result, the interaction between the subject and the subject changes, the student begins to play the role of an active subject who studies the latest experience, conducts scientific research, adopts modern technologies, and professionally approves the latest discoveries.

The model of formation of information-modeling skills of future engineers includes the formation of the following groups:

1. General intellectual skills: analysis of received data, comparison of events, establishment of cause-and-effect relationships, classification, algorithmization, prediction of the production process, synthesis of information, generalization of knowledge.

2. General didactic skills: setting activity goals, encouraging positive motivation in the work process, organizing one's own research activities, designing the production process, organizing and managing team development situations, skills to use information technology opportunities, various sources of information in the production process and independent work with databases.

3. Skills and qualifications of an engineer in special disciplines: the ability to develop an enterprise strategy to achieve the highest production

efficiency and quality of work in the organization of transportation of passengers, cargo, goods; analysis of the state of existing management systems, development of measures to eliminate shortcomings, modeling of management methods, development and implementation of optimal transport and technological schemes for the delivery of goods based on the principles of logistics; effective use of material, financial and human resources in the implementation of specific and defined tasks.

A new view of engineering activity modeling with the possibility of entering the socio-cultural sphere - which goes beyond the traditional scheme of "science-engineering activity-production" and covers various types of social practice and enters the field of education, service, independent professional culture of a modern specialist-engineer circulation is of socio-technical importance.

The socio-technical relationship of modeling affects all areas of engineering and the entire technosphere.

The formation of information-modeling skills is the result of the formation of general cultural and professional skills of students necessary for the implementation of professional activities in the field of transport process technology. In the educational process, it is desirable to use modeling technologies that provide a differentiated approach to teaching, taking into account the level of intellectual development of students, their readiness, abilities and opportunities.

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